

“A study on Perceived Effect of Digital Marketing on Online Shopping among youth in Belthangady taluk of Dakshina Kannada”

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Abstract

Creating brand awareness and communicating benefits or values to the end customers is the first and most important objective of every business. Development of technologies has made the task of every business easy, and more challenging due to increasing competition. Digital marketing enables interaction between consumers and producers in the marketing process. The broad objective of this study is to ascertain the relationship between the perceived awareness of digital marketing and benefits with buying decision. The study made use of sample of fifty young respondents in Ujire(belthangady). Cross sectional research was adopted to gather data. Findings of the study noted that perceived awareness and benefits of digital marketing positively related with the online shopping decisions of youngsters.

Keywords: Digital marketing, buying decision, shopping.

Introduction

The rapidly emerging technology have made it important for organisation to adopt and revolve with changing technology to remain competitive. Digital technology poses new challenges and opportunities for marketers through digital platform. Customers can access millions of information of the products and services at any time and any place. Digital marketing platform enables organisation to reach customers, and to stay connected with customers around the clock. Extensive dependency on technology by the customer made organisation to operate their business through digital platform. Digitalisation of production and marketing initiatives ensures optimum utilization of resource and enhances efficiency.

The development and widespread use of digital technologies have transformed the way of life and mode of communication in the daily and professional life. Digital communication tool enabled the people to access the data or information regardless of social status. Today customers empowered and buyer bargaining power strengthened as a result of easy access to information through digital platform like, Facebook, Twitter, microblogs, and search engine etc. Digital systems enable the users to exchange information over the internet for free of cost within the limited time. Today digital communication tools are used as most powerful marketing techniques to attract and retain the customers. Digital marketing significantly influence on the consumers buying decision (Stanley, A., & Chinelo, A. (2017). At the organisational perspective digital platform provides cost effective mode of communication. Digital marketing is the employment of electronic media to promote product and service of the organisation. Internet based media used as a core promotional

measures in addition to mobile, traditional TV and radio by the organisation.

More than 34 percent of business had already adopted to integrated digital marketing system by 2016 and 72 percent of marketers believe that their company revenue grow by 30 percent and traditional marketing no longer sufficient competitive. Cost of reaching 2000 audience in traditional marketing likely be \$150 in broadcast, \$250 in newspaper, \$500 in magazine and \$900 through direct marketing. Whereas digital marketing cost much less to reach 2000 audience, i.e. \$50 in websearch and \$75 through social networking.

Digital marketing and Business

Digital marketing gained its significance in the present business as it offers equal opportunity for all kinds of business, more cost effective than traditional marketing, more conversion rate (conversion of non-consumers to consumers) helps to generate better revenue (2.8 times better revenue growth), facilitates interaction with target audience, easily caters to the mobile consumer, enables to offer sustainable fashion and build brand through social reviews and testimonials. Digital marketing also helps the organisation to understand the customers satisfaction with product helps in product differentiation and also matter a lot in the process of Business to Business and Business to Customers relationship building.

Digital marketing and customers

Digital marketing has changed customers shopping attitude and habits. Digital platforms have empowered customer with access to billions of information about the product and services. People access into websites, social medias, and also get feedback from friends, peer, retailers about the product. Social platform provides rich source of feedback and ratings which form the buying behaviour of customers.

Customers are benefited from the digital marketing in many ways:

1. Customers can access and compare the prices, features and attractive offers of product using the company or online shopping websites.
2. Transparent pricing available at all times (24X7)
3. Tracking purchase and delivering data is possible.
4. Easy grievance settlement system.
5. Opportunities to exchange the product.

Literature Review

1. **Buchanan, L., Kelly, B., & Yeatman, H. (2017).**This study analysed the impact of online marketing in enhancing the young adults interest, attitude and intension to purchase of energy drink. Experimental group was examined through surveys and semi-structured interviews after providing exposure to two popular energy drinks websites and social media sites. Study found that pretest attitude and purchase intention of participants of control group and experimental group towards energy drink were similar but post test revealed that experimental group had shown significantly better attitude towards the two energy drinks(Red bull and V energy) than the control group participants.
2. **Sivasankaran, S. (2017).**This study examined the influence of digital marketing on the buying behaviour of youth. Study revealed that conveniency of information offered through social media,quick shopping provision, attractiveness and quality of information available on website and feedback of public significantly influence the buying behaviour of youth.
3. **Stanley, A., & Chinelo, A. (2017).**This study determined the effect of digital marketing on customer Satisfaction in Nigerian deposit money banks. Cross structural survey results revealed that regular communication through email showed highly significant correlation with customer satisfaction. Regression analysis

exhibited the significant positive effect of digital marketing on consumer satisfaction.

4. **Firmalar, K., Fark, M., Amac, Y., Pazarlama, D., & De, E. S. (2015).**The result indicated that housing companies are using paid digital content, corporate website, search engine pages, email communication etc which creates greater impact than those of proactive content (social media) and also found that digital marketing tools such as Facebook and twitter will create better brand awareness and will become important in future due to its cost effectiveness and quickness.

Objectives

1. To understand the perceived awareness and benefits of digital market among youth.
2. To analyse the relationship between perceived awareness and received benefit of digital marketing with buying decision.

Hypothesis

1. There is no significance relationship between perceived awareness of digital marketing and buying decision.
2. There is no significant relationship between perceived benefits of digital marketing and buying decision.

Methodology

1. **Sample:** The present study consists of **50** young respondents living in **Ujire, Belthangady talluk** located in **Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka** selected based on the purposive sampling method.
2. **Criteria Procedure:** Respondents for the study chosen are the youngsters.Self-reportingquestionnaire was distributed to those who use digital technology like android mobile and social medias like Facebook and having experience in online shopping.
3. **Research design.** The study is **empirical** in nature and adopted **survey method**
4. **Analysis:** Collected using self-reporting questionnaire was coded and tabulated using excel and further hypotheses was tested though **SPSS software.**

Data analysis and Interpretations

Table 1.Demographic profile

Factor	Criteria	Number of respondents	percentage
Gender	Male	22	44%
	Female	28	56%
Age	20-25	40	80%
	26-31	4	8%
	32-35	6	12%
	36 and above	0	0%
Qualification	PUC	0	0%
	Degree	42	84%
	Post Graduate	5	10%

	Other	3	6%
Occupation	Student	37	74%
	Teacher	10	20%
	Entrepreneur	1	2%
	Professional	1	2%
	Other	1	2%

Source: Primary Data: Demographic profile of the respondents revealed that 56 percent of the respondents are female and 44 percent of the respondents are male, and majority (80%) of the respondents are aged between 20-25, 84 per cent of the respondents are graduates and majority (74%) of the respondents are students.

Analysis: Collected data was coded and tabulated using excel and later statistical analysis was done

using S.P.S.S. software- Hypothesis drawn was tested through Kendall's tau-b (τ_b). Kendall's tau-b (τ_b) correlation coefficient (Kendall's tau-b, for short) is a nonparametric measure of the strength and direction of association that exists between two variables measured on at least an ordinal scale. It is considered a nonparametric alternative to the Pearson's correlation

Table 2- Perceived awareness and buying decision

Correlations				
			Perceived Awareness	Buying Decision
Kendall's tau_b	Perceived Awareness	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.232*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.034
		N	50	50
	Buying Decision	Correlation Coefficient	.232*	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.034	.
		N	50	50
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).				

The above table shows the result of hypothesis analysis of relationship between perceived awareness of digital marketing initiatives and buying decision. The correlation coefficient between perceived awareness of digital marketing and buying

decision of consumers is positive ($\tau_b=0.232$, $p=0.034<0.05$). This indicates that, perceived awareness of digital marketing is positively related with buying behaviour of consumer.

Table 3 Perceived benefit and buying decision

Correlations				
			Perceived Benefit	Buying Decision
Kendall's tau_b	Perceived Benefit	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.238*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.025
		N	50	50
	Buying Decision	Correlation Coefficient	.238*	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.025	.
		N	50	50
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).				

The table shows the result of hypothesis analysis of relationship between perceived benefits of digital marketing and buying decision. The correlation coefficient between perceived benefits of digital marketing and buying decision of consumer is positive ($\tau_b=0.238$) and it is significant at the level of 0.05. ($p=0.025<0.05$). This shows that there is significant positive relationship between perceive

benefits of digital marketing and buying behaviour of consumer.

Findings and Suggestions

The findings of this study demonstrate that perceived awareness and perceived benefits of digital marketing have significant relationship with buying decision. Perceived awareness of digital communication keep the customer updated about the

new trends, fashion, new offers and made by the marketers. Awareness of digital marketing initiatives enhances the customer's convenience in purchasing decision. Perceived benefits of digital marketing also minimise the shopping time, cost, provides wide product and services options and provision of trial use and return option if the product do not meet the expectation.

Conclusion

The consumers who use the digital platform like social media, web sites, email etc. will have adverse set of characteristics. Digital marketing facilitates customer in product purchase before entering to the physical retail outlet or online outlets. Information gathered by the customer through digital media or digital marketing initiatives of firms help to evaluate alternative and finalise their choice. Based on the findings noted above, enhanced awareness and perceived benefits of digital marketing, maximises the intension of buying a product or services online. Favourable and rich information makes consumer decisions more easy, which also improves quality of life.

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